

THE IMPACT OF THE INDIVIDUALIZED LEARNING PLAN ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN THE PRIMARY AND PRESCHOOL PEDAGOGY PROGRAMME

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Abstract

This study highlights the formative value of the individualized learning plan in the initial preparation of future teachers, by investigating its impact on the academic performance of students enrolled in the Primary and Preschool Pedagogy (PIPP) programme at the University of Craiova.

The research was based on an experimental design involving two student groups – an experimental group and a control group – the first benefiting from a structured individualized learning plan. Data collection was carried out through pedagogical experiment and document analysis. The results confirm the research hypothesis, demonstrating that individualized learning has a significant positive

influence on students' academic performance. The article provides an updated theoretical foundation, including the contemporary role of artificial intelligence in personalizing learning in higher education.

Keywords: individualized learning plan, academic performance, initial teacher education, artificial intelligence, personalized learning

Introduction

Individualized instruction represents one of the major directions of educational modernization, as it reflects the transition from teacher-centered instruction to student-centered learning. In classical terms, Legrand (1971) conceptualized individualization as a reorganization of the learning process in such a way that enables each learner to progress at their own pace and according to their personal potential. At university level, this approach becomes essential, as student teachers must experience individualized learning models in order to later implement them with children.

Recent pedagogical literature (Căprioară & Frunză, 2013) defines individualized learning as a complex process that requires an alignment between instructional content, learning strategies and assessment methods, while taking into account the specific characteristics of each learner. Popescu (2013) emphasizes that modern education needs to move from “a school for all” to “a school for each individual”, meaning that teachers must develop flexible instructional designs that respond to learner diversity. Mialaret (1991) also notes that individualized activities enable the identification of student difficulties, support differentiated intervention and help maintain learning motivation.

In the context of today's technological society, individualized learning can no longer be separated from the digital dimension. Wagner (2012) argues that contemporary education must move beyond memorization and focus instead on the ability to use knowledge creatively and efficiently. The development of

artificial intelligence (AI) technologies has significantly enhanced the possibilities of individualized instruction, enabling adaptive recommendation systems, automated feedback and personalized learning trajectories.

International organizations such as OECD (2021) and UNESCO (2023) highlight that AI does not replace the teacher, but strengthens their capacity to monitor learning, identify risk situations, and differentiate instruction based on real-time data. For future teachers in primary and preschool education, familiarity with these tools becomes a professional requirement, as they will increasingly work in technologically enriched learning environments.

Methodology

Participants

The research sample consisted of 50 third-year students enrolled in the Primary and Preschool Pedagogy (PIPP) programme at the University of Craiova. The students were divided into two groups: a control group, which followed conventional learning activities, and an experimental group, which worked according to an individualized learning plan. Prior to the intervention, both groups demonstrated comparable academic levels, confirmed by initial testing.

Methods

The principal method used was the **pedagogical experiment**, carried out in the structure pre-test – intervention – post-test. In addition, a **document analysis** was conducted on the individualized learning plans produced by the students. Statistical data processing was performed using IBM SPSS version 21.

Instruments

The following instruments were used:

- an initial and final assessment test evaluating competencies related to lesson planning and instructional design,
- a grid-based evaluation tool for analysing individualized learning plans,

- students' digital learning portfolios and progress records.

Results and Discussion

The initial assessment results indicated no statistically significant differences between the two groups. After implementing the individualized learning plan, the experimental group recorded a substantial improvement in academic outcomes: 76% of students obtained advanced performance levels, compared with 52% in the control group. Moreover, no student in the experimental group remained below the minimum competence threshold, while 12% of the control group did.

Analysis of the 47 individualized plans revealed that 59.6% of students in the experimental group fully accomplished their learning tasks, 57.4% demonstrated originality and creativity, and 63.8% displayed accurate and coherent academic language. These findings support existing literature showing that involving learners in personalized planning increases their motivation and self-regulation (Hulleman & Harackiewicz, 2009).

The results align with recent studies on AI-supported personalized learning (Holmes et al., 2022), which demonstrate that technological tools can optimize instructional differentiation and reduce academic discrepancies within student cohorts.

Conclusions

The study confirms the hypothesis according to which the individualized learning plan has a positive impact on the development of pedagogical competencies and academic results of students enrolled in teacher-training programs. The findings indicate that student involvement in designing and monitoring their own learning pathways strengthens academic performance and self-regulated learning.

The research contributes to the literature by:

- providing empirical evidence regarding individualized learning in teacher education;
- integrating artificial intelligence perspectives into pedagogical analysis;
- demonstrating the effectiveness of learning personalization in higher education.

Future research directions include expanding the intervention to other university levels, integrating AI tutoring systems into pedagogical practice and developing digital adaptive learning models tailored to teacher education.

Research limitations include the reduced sample size, the single institutional context, and the limited duration of the intervention. However, the findings provide valid arguments for incorporating individualized learning plans systematically in initial teacher training program

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